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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF A PREDIABETES PROTOCOL FOR DIABETES PREVENTION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Type 2 Diabetes (T2DM) is a daunting diagnosis associated with multiple comorbidities. Prediabetes remains a major predisposing factor in the development of T2DM. Therefore, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC] (2021a) developed a Diabetes prevention program (DPP) to combat the increasing number of those diagnosed with T2DM. There has been sufficient evidence that supports the effectiveness of DPPs in preventing T2DM along with other benefits, including a decrease in weight, body mass index (BMI), and blood pressure. Yet, these programs remain under-used. This pilot DPP project aimed to improve the clinic's current process and evaluate the effectiveness of weekly classes on diabetes prevention based on the CDC's DPP. Participants included adults over the age of 18. Participant variables in the project included hemoglobin A1c (Hgb A1c), weight, BMI, blood pressure, and a self-reported questionnaire. Five out of seven participants completed the project. There was an overall decrease in weight, BMI, Hgb A1c, and blood pressure. Additionally, there was an increase in the questionnaire scores that reflected an increase in healthy eating habits, highlighting the importance of lifestyle changes in diabetes prevention and a healthy lifestyle overall.

Keywords: T2DM, prediabetes, DPP, Hgb A1c, BMI, and weight.

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Background

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a serious and chronic health condition affecting nearly 40 million Americans nationwide (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2022c). In T2DM, there is a disruption in the body's ability to respond to insulin, thus causing insulin resistance. In response to insulin resistance, the pancreas attempts to overcompensate by creating more insulin; eventually, the pancreas cannot sustain the demand, and the amount of glucose rises in the blood, causing hyperglycemia (CDC, 2022). Furthermore, increased glucose in the blood can lead to kidney disease, vision loss, cardiovascular disease, limb amputations, and stroke. Moreover, it is estimated that the annual cost of diabetes care in the United States is over 300 billion dollars annually (CDC, 2021). It is also important to note that because T2DM puts patients at risk for and is commonly associated with other comorbidities, it increases the possibility of depression due to multimorbidity (Wang et al., 2022).

Moreover, people with T2DM are twice as likely to suffer from depression than those without the disease. Thus, T2DM is a costly disease with serious health risks that can significantly burden one's physical and emotional health. Therefore, healthcare providers should make every effort to prevent the diagnosis altogether. T2DM continues to have a high prevalence among adults and the elderly, with over 50% of individuals over 65 affected (Kramer et al., 2018). Unfortunately, prediabetes and T2DM have been increasing among children and adolescents, with high-risk groups having a 50% likelihood of developing T2DM in their lifetime (Peña et al., 2022). Since prediabetes and T2DM affect various populations, enforcing preventive measures and encouraging healthy lifestyles is necessary.

The diagnosis of prediabetes is made when the amount of glucose in the blood is above the normal levels for Hemoglobin A1C (HgbA1c) 5.7-6.4%, but not elevated enough to make the

diagnosis of T2DM (HgbA1c >6.5%) (CDC, 2021). Prediabetes affects a vast majority of the population, with nearly 100 million Americans living affected, yet most people are unaware they have the condition (CDC, 2021). Due to the severe health implications T2DM has on one's health, it is imperative to focus on preventative measures and act at the diagnosis of prediabetes before the development of T2DM. Moreover, although prediabetes is a significant risk factor for developing diabetes, it is crucial to understand that the diagnosis is reversible (CDC, 2021). Research has supported that lifestyle changes, including diet and exercise, can impede the diagnosis of T2DM (MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022).

Additionally, research supports that lifestyle changes can decrease glucose levels and significantly reduce weight in individuals, decreasing the incidence of other comorbidities (American Diabetes Association [ADA], 2020; CDC, 2021a; O'Brien et al., 2017). Due to the positive impact lifestyle changes have on an individual's outcome, healthcare professionals must educate and provide a foundation for their patients' success in the prevention of diabetes and reversal of prediabetes. DPPs and lifestyle change programs are options that providers can utilize for patients if there is no such protocol or support in the clinic. DPPs provide a structuralized lifestyle change program that is CDC-approved, provides group support for a year, and a personalized lifestyle coach (CDC, 2021a). Moreover, DPPs can decrease the risk of developing diabetes by nearly 60% in adults and over 70% in those 60 and older.

CDC and Medicare developed the Medicare Diabetes Prevention Program (MDPP) and have it available as a covered benefit (Katula et al., 2022). Despite this, half of the patients have reported not receiving referrals or education on diabetes prevention (Katula et al., 2022). Although data confirms lifestyle changes' efficacy in avoiding

T2DM, there is a gap in the resources needed, as seen by the absence of referrals and education. Although there is evidence that DPPs are effective, prediabetic intervention is not the standard of care in healthcare facilities. Moreover, if DPP is not a covered benefit or option for the patient, they would benefit from lifestyle interventions, and education is warranted at diagnosis. Therefore, healthcare providers and healthcare facilities must do their part in offering DPP or prediabetes educational support protocols at the diagnosis of prediabetes in hopes of preventing the progression of T2DM.

Problem Statement

The clinic where the project occurred had an overall six-month health program. Patients are referred to the program when diagnosed with elevated cholesterol, prediabetes, overweight, or obesity. However, no prediabetes protocol or evidence-based year-long diabetes prevention programs (DPP) were being utilized. Therefore, in addition to disease management already in place, the project aimed to focus on diabetes prevention via a pilot diabetes prevention program.

Purpose Statement

This project aimed to outline the severe health risks attached to the diagnosis of T2DM and highlight the benefits that DPPs and lifestyle interventions have on an individual's health and in the prevention of T2DM. Therefore, this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aimed to develop, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based prediabetes protocol, including a pilot DPP targeting prediabetic patients in a Los Angeles, California, primary care clinic. The overall goals of this project included improving care for prediabetic patients and linking them to evidence-based prevention services to reduce the risk of the development of T2DM.

Theoretical Framework: The Health Belief Model

Theoretical frameworks are significant because they enhance the research process by offering a roadmap for understanding the study subject in greater detail (Lynch et al., 2020). Further, using a theoretical framework might increase the probability that the research topic was successfully addressed. The Health Belief Model (HBM) (Figure 1) is the theoretical framework employed in this DNP project to guide the application of evidence-based DPPs in diabetes prevention. Social psychologists developed the HBM approximately 70 years ago to comprehend why people neglected to participate in the available programs to detect and prevent disease (Champion & Skinner, 2008). The HBM is one of the most utilized conceptual frameworks for understanding health-related behaviors (Champion & Skinner, 2008). Over the past 30 years, the HBM has since expanded and has been used to examine and provide a foundation for interventions in disease prevention (Champion & Skinner, 2008). Moreover, the HBM utilizes constructs to analyze further why individuals choose to participate in health prevention, act in controlling their disease, and participate in screening for disease prevention.

Health Belief Model Constructs and Application of HBM in Diabetes Prevention

According to the HBM, people are more likely to take action to avoid a disease if they are aware of the consequences of the disease (Dumitrescu & Iacob, 2021). Furthermore, there are multiple constructs in the HBM to prognosticate the actions individuals take in disease prevention, and they include “susceptibility, seriousness, benefits, and barriers to a behavior, cures to action, and most recently, self-efficacy” (Champion & Skinner, 2008, p. 46).

In the HBM, *Perceived Susceptibility* & *Perceived Severity* are also known as *Perceived Threat*. *Perceived Susceptibility* is the belief in the likelihood of disease development. In the case of this project, the prediction was that if an individual was informed about the risk of developing

diabetes, they would be more inclined to participate in a DPP (Champion & Skinner, 2008).

Perceived severity is one's belief in the seriousness of a disease. Moreover, if an individual understands the severe consequences of diabetes, they will take the necessary steps to prevent the disease from occurring. In applying *Perceived Susceptibility* to this DNP project, the at-risk population was prediabetic patients, and risk was personalized based on individual characteristics (Champion & Skinner, 2008). Additionally, by applying *Perceived Severity*, individuals were informed of the severe repercussions of having a diabetes diagnosis to encourage participation in a DPP. This includes their risk for developing microvascular and macrovascular complications such as the increased risk of stroke, blindness, limb amputations, myocardial infarction, renal failure, and other possible comorbidities (CDC, 2022c).

Perceived benefits are the individual's beliefs about the positive effects of their actions in disease prevention (Champion & Skinner, 2008). Moreover, people are more likely to participate in disease prevention if they believe their efforts' results are beneficial. In this project, if the individual thinks lifestyle changes, such as a balanced diet and regular exercise, can prevent diabetes, they will participate in the DPP. The participants were informed about the necessary activities and the potential advantages of participating in DPP when applied to practice and in this DNP project.

Any unfavorable effects of their health efforts are called *Perceived Barriers* (Champion & Skinner, 2008). Perceived barriers can include expenses, time commitments, or any action that can be viewed as inconvenient. Therefore, the *Perceived Threat* drives a person's motivation to ignore real or imagined obstacles and perform the necessary health activities (Champion & Skinner, 2008). To address *Perceived Barriers*, the participants received the appropriate education, concerns about misinformation or anxieties were discussed and correctly managed,

they were guided on how to handle these hurdles, and necessary support was given when this was put into practice in this DNP project (Champion & Skinner, 2008).

Methods used to promote individual preparation are known as *Cues to Action* (Champion & Skinner, 2008). *Cues to Action* in this DNP project included frequent follow-ups, educational classes, and awareness of prediabetes and the potentially negative consequences of a diabetes diagnosis.

As mentioned, self-efficacy is one of the recently introduced constructs in the HBM (Champion & Skinner, 2008). Self-efficacy describes a person's confidence in participating in healthy behaviors. Therefore, to encourage the individual's confidence in this DNP project, the participants were provided direction, reasonable goals were made, support and encouragement were provided, and any fears or worries were addressed.

Other Variables include socioeconomics, sociodemographic elements, education, structural variables, knowledge, and sociopsychological factors. The modifying factors in this DNP project include demographic, clinical, and socioeconomic factors.

Health Belief Model Literature Review

The HBM (Appendix A) has been used in various contexts to better understand health behaviors in disease prevention. As mentioned previously, prediabetes affects nearly 100 million Americans nationwide; despite this, there is a lack of utilization of DPPs in practice. Hence, assessing if people would participate in the program if it were available to prediabetic patients is crucial. According to Joiner et al. (2022), DPPs should be more available, yet in clinics that had DPPs accessible, less than 2.4% of Americans enrolled. Moreover, underutilization of DPPs could be attributed to the need for more awareness of prediabetes, as only 13% revealed they had been informed about their condition. In addition, less than 4% of individuals reported being referred to a lifestyle intervention program (Joiner et al., 2022). Therefore, the researchers in the study by Joiner et al. (2022) sought to evaluate the connections between domains of the HBM and DPP enrolment to maximize efforts to prevent the diagnosis of type 2 diabetes. The researchers found that two constructs of the HBM were associated with enrollments in the DPP: perceived benefits and strong cues to actions increased participation in a DPP (Joiner et al., 2022). Therefore, educating individuals on the benefits of enrollment and providing support and guidance can encourage enrollment and success. It is important to note that in this study, perceived threat and self-efficacy were not driving factors for enrollment.

In an RCT by Githinji et al. (2022), the researchers examined the effectiveness of culturally sensitive education in diabetes prevention and management based on the HBM. There were statistically significant findings among the intervention group that presented with increased knowledge of diabetes, perceived benefits, perceived susceptibility, self-efficacy, and increased intake of healthy foods (Githinji et al., 2022). Moreover, it is essential to note that weight change, physical activity, or perceived barriers had no significant findings. The results are in

favor of the potential advantages of a diabetes education program and the beneficial impacts it may have on food habits, health attitudes, and diabetes awareness.

HBM in patients with Type 2 Diabetes

Since the literature supports positive findings regarding the utilization of HBM in prediabetic patients, evaluating how the model can also benefit disease management is essential. In the randomized controlled trial (RCT) by Mohammadi et al. (2018), the researchers investigated the benefits of promoting self-efficacy education for diabetes management. The participants in the intervention group presented with significantly greater glycemic benchmarks and improved quality of life compared with the control group (Mohammadi et al., 2018). These findings support the idea that self-efficacy education can improve glycemic control and the patient's quality of life. In addition, Shabibi et al. (2017) conducted a quasi-experimental study to investigate the impact of an instructional program based on the HBM geared toward diabetes management. The study's findings were statistically significant across all HBM components, indicating that education interventions using the HBM as a theoretical guiding framework have improved self-care management in diabetes control (Shabibi et al., 2017).

To conclude, prediabetes is a risk factor in the development of T2DM, and DPPs have aided in diabetes prevention. Various studies support that the HBM can guide practice studies to improve outcomes in preventing and managing diabetes (Shabibi et al., 2017; Mohammadi et al., 2018). Using the HBM as a theory to guide and support the DPP intervention for this project is supported by evidence in the literature reporting findings of programs aimed at reducing the risk of T2DM among pre-diabetic patients in outpatient settings. Understanding and educating prediabetic patients at risk of developing T2DM about the importance of diabetes prevention is essential for motivating individuals to participate in diabetes prevention activities, such as DPPs.

Given that the HBM has been demonstrated to be effective as a theoretical framework to guide DPP interventions in outpatient settings, this model will be used to frame and guide this DNP project (Appendix B).

Literature Review

This project aims to outline the severe health risks attached to the diagnosis of T2DM and highlight the benefits that DPPs and lifestyle interventions have on an individual's health and in the prevention of T2DM. Therefore, this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aims to develop, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based prediabetes protocol, including a pilot DPP targeting prediabetic patients in a Los Angeles, California, primary care clinic. The overall goals of this project include improving care for prediabetic patients and linking them to evidence-based prevention services to reduce the risk of the development of T2DM.

Search Strategy

Before establishing a DPP in a primary care clinic, a literature search was launched using the electronic databases Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Search (CINAHL), California State University, Fullerton Library OneSearch, and PubMed. The following search phrases were used: "prediabetes," "diabetes prevention," and "DPP." Additionally, the following co-terms were used in the search: "DPP and randomized controlled trial (RCT)," "diabetes prevention and RCT," and "prediabetes and RCT." The populated results were thoroughly reviewed to ensure relevancy to the topic. Article references were manually searched for additional potentially pertinent literature for this DNP project. Inclusion criteria included English articles, peer-reviewed, and publication dates between 2017 and 2023. Further inclusion criteria included research papers on prediabetic patients, DPP, and lifestyle change programs.

Although this DNP project will be focused on adults with prediabetes, this was not limited in the search. The search was open to all genders and racial and ethnic groups. Moreover, the search was available to the pediatric population as rates of prediabetes and T2DM have increased in this population, and they could benefit from this information. Excluded articles included non-English research, Type 1 diabetes articles, pregnant women, as this project will not cover gestational diabetes, and articles published before 2017 to capture the most up-to-date evidence. The CDC, ADA, and World Health Organization [WHO] were also explored to incorporate relevant clinical practice guideline recommendations.

Search Results

This literature review will encompass 17 studies (Appendix C); 14 randomized controlled trials (Ben-Yacov et al., 2021; Das et al., 2022; Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Shamizadeh et al., 2019; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020; Velluzzi et al., 2022), one pilot RCT (Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022), a pilot mixed methods cluster RCT (Keck et al., 2020), and one quasi-experimental study (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020). In addition, two of the RCTs reviewed targeted the health effects of digital DPPs and used CDC DPP as a guide for their digital DPP (Katula et al., 2022; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). In the RCT by Staite et al. (2020), the researchers sought to investigate the effects of a fully mobile DPP with no health coaching. In comparison, the researchers in the RCT by Kramer et al. (2018) sought to investigate the health benefits of a DPP among older adults and offered the program with the option of face-to-face or fully digital delivery. The following topics organized key themes within the studies included in this review: 1) DPP interventions and lifestyle programs, 2) evidence-based nutritional and physical activity recommendations, and 3) mode of program

delivery. Furthermore, the pathophysiology of prediabetes and T2DM progression will be discussed, along with associated complications.

Pathophysiology of T2DM

Understanding the underlying pathophysiology of T2DM is vital in any prevention interventions targeting prediabetes. T2DM is an epidemic of vast proportions attached to life-threatening comorbidities affecting over 40 million people in the US (Dartarian & Bowen, 2019; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022; Shamuzadeh et al., 2019;). To understand T2DM and prevention, it is imperative to understand the pathophysiology of the disease. The body uses blood glucose for energy, and insulin is the pancreatic hormone that regulates blood glucose levels (Robertson & Udler, 2021; WHO, 2022). As previously mentioned, T2DM is a chronic disease that occurs when there is a disruption in the body's usual response to insulin (CDC, 2021; WHO, 2022). Moreover, the pathogenesis of T2DM involves two potential causes outlined below.

First, the pancreas no longer generates enough insulin, which causes a rise in blood glucose, resulting in an abnormally high level of glucose in the bloodstream (CDC, 2021; WHO, 2022). Second, the body can no longer efficiently utilize its created insulin, leading to increased circulating blood glucose and hyperglycemia. Therefore, the pathogenesis for the development of T2DM involves insulin resistance and the impairment of insulin secretion (Robertson & Udler, 2021). Elevated glucose levels can cause significant health consequences; thus, healthcare practitioners must intervene in the diagnosis of prediabetes, and this should be a top priority for public health (CDC, 2021; ADA, 2020).

Prediabetes Millions of Americans are diagnosed with prediabetes each year, and the prevalence of the disease is still rising (Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022; CDC, 2021; Dartarian &

Bowen, 2019; Dorans et al., 2022; Shamuzadeh et al., 2019; Toro Ramos et al., 2020).

Prediabetes is diagnosed when there is an elevated amount of glucose in the blood; however, the amount of glucose is not significant enough to diagnose T2DM. The diagnosis of T2DM can be made in various ways, including fasting blood glucose (FBG) of 126 or greater, HgbA1c >6.5%, and oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) of greater than 200 mg/dl (ADA, n.d.; CDC, 2023).

Prediabetes is diagnosed when FBG is between 100-125, HgbA1c of 5.7-6.4%, and OGTT between 140-199 (ADA, n.d.; CDC, 2023; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020; Peña et al., 2022). It is important to note that prediabetes remains a predominant risk factor for T2DM and is reversible. According to the HBM, if a person is aware of the perceived threat of their diagnosis, they will be more likely to take preventative actions. While prediabetes is reversible and T2DM effects can be severe, identifying potential complications of T2DM and conveying them to patients is critical in preventing T2DM.

Complications of T2DM and Associated Costs

T2DM is a severe condition that remains the eighth cause of mortality and is a significant contributor to disability nationwide (CDC, 2022a; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). T2DM is linked to a slew of diseases as well as both microvascular and macrovascular complications. Macrovascular complications include myocardial infarction and stroke, while microvascular complications include kidney disease, limb amputations due to neuropathy, and blindness (CDC, 2020; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022; Shamuzadeh et al., 2019; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020; WHO, 2022). Furthermore, those with T2DM are up to three times more likely to have a myocardial infarction or stroke than an individual who does not have the disease (WHO, 2022).

Moreover, T2DM is one of the leading causes of chronic kidney disease; patients with diabetes are also more likely to acquire severe consequences from infectious disease processes,

as was recently witnessed during the COVID-19 pandemic (CDC, 2020). Additionally, the microvascular changes can cause damage to the blood vessels in the eye, causing diabetic retinopathy and glaucoma, which can lead to blindness (CDC, 2022a; WHO, 2022). Lastly, the microvascular changes cause reduced blood flow and nerve damage, which causes diabetic ulcers, decreased sensations, and delayed healing that can lead to limb amputations (CDC, 2022a; WHO, 2022).

Unsurprisingly, the expenditures associated with T2DM and T2DM complications are astounding. For instance, it is expected that the annual cost of diabetes and related expenditures would exceed 300 billion in the United States alone and that each person's annual cost of managing their diabetes is around 500 dollars (CDC, 2021; Dartarian & Bowen, 2019; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). This is of significant concern, considering that the CDC estimates that by the year 2050, over 30% of Americans will be diagnosed with T2DM. As a result, it is vital to investigate the harmful effects of diabetes on the community and potential health-related expenses that may be difficult to manage. Therefore, it is imperative to examine ways that diabetes can be prevented. According to current research, lifestyle interventions and DPPs can reduce the advancement of a T2DM diagnosis by more than 50% in individuals and potentially over 70% in persons over the age of 60 (CDC, 2021; Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Kramer et al., 2018; O' Brien et al., 2017; Shamizedeh et al., 2019; Staite et al., 2020; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020; Velluzzi et al., 2022; 2020). Therefore, understanding the structure of DPPs is crucial to guide the patient in their success of T2DM prevention.

DPPs and Lifestyle Intervention Programs

To address the increased prevalence of T2DM and prediabetes, the CDC launched the National DPP in 2010 (CDC, 2021). This review of the literature comprised eight RCTs and one

quasi-experimental study evaluating DPPs and lifestyle intervention programs to inform project development and implementation (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). Additionally, these studies incorporated the CDC DPP curriculum as a source for their research and program adaptations (CDC, 2021; Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). Various studies adapted the DPPs and lifestyle change programs to target their populations (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2021; Fritsche et al., 2021; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). The study designs, populations analyzed, sample sizes, study characteristics, and interventions will be discussed below. The details of the studies, measures, and effectiveness of these interventions will be addressed in a subsequent section.

Design and Interventions

Research supports that lifestyle interventions, including diet and exercise, are an effective strategy to delay the progression of T2DM and can be delivered via DPPs or lifestyle intervention programs (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). The CDC DPP is a 12-month interactive program focusing on nutrition and physical activity, and the educational material is delivered via instructional sessions accompanied by check-ins with a lifestyle coach (CDC, 2022). The curriculum includes 26 modules and recommends weekly meetings for the first four months, biweekly for the next two months, and then once monthly for the remaining six months (CDC, 2022). Additionally, the

CDC offers lifestyle coaches the opportunity to undergo approved CDC training, which any individual can complete with no degree required (CDC, 2022).

All eight RCTs that implemented DPPs and lifestyle programs aligned with CDC recommendations of offering the interventional program over a year (CDC, 2021; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). The current recommendation for physical activity is 150 min/per week and was recommended across eight studies (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Shamizadeh et al., 2019; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020; Velluzzi et al., 2022;). In contrast, the researchers in the study by Fritsche et al. (2021) focused on intensified lifestyle interventions and recommended 360 minutes of weekly activity in the intervention group. Additionally, research supports that not one diet can be recommended for every individual, which will be discussed in further detail below (Ben-Yacov et al., 2021; Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022; Dorans et al., 2022; Evert et al., 2019). However, encouragement of a healthy diet with educational material on a balanced diet was used consistently across all the research analyzed (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020).

The CDC states that any individual can teach the DPP program and have the opportunity to undergo training, and a degree or license is not a requirement. Across the studies, various professionals taught the educational classes (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). Additionally, Daftarian and Bowen's (2020) was the only reviewed study that opted for a nurse practitioner (NP)-led program. In comparison, two RCTs

opted for trained lifestyle coaches (Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018). In the RCT by Das et al. (2020), the interventionists offered education and check-ins. In contrast, the researchers in the RCT by Fritsche et al. (2021) used a dietician for their educational sessions, while the researchers in the RCT by Toro-Ramos et al. (2020) provided a CDC DPP-trained Noom coach for their digital DPP. Moreover, the researchers in the RCT by Staite et al. (2020) opted for a fully digital DPP with no lifestyle coach and instead sent motivational SMS text messages. Interestingly, this was the only study with no statistically significant findings (Staite et al., 2020).

A commonality in the studies by O'Brien et al. (2017) and Peña et al. (2022) was that they employed community health workers to deliver education in a culturally appropriate manner by ensuring education was delivered in their primary language. Community health professionals are a cost-effective alternative for providing diabetes education and can be trained in conducting classes, particularly bilingual community workers who can educate Spanish-speaking patients (O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022). Except for the study by Staite et al. (2020), the included studies presented statistically significant findings that will be discussed in further detail below. Moreover, research supports the flexibility of teaching educational sessions, which might motivate additional primary care clinics to offer a DPP.

Three RCTs utilized social cognitive theory (SCT) as their framework for their intervention delivery (Das et al., 2021; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022; Shamizadeh et al., 2019). Furthermore, the researchers in the study by Das et al. (2021) compared DPP to an SCT-based Healthy Weight for Living (HWL) program for weight loss among military members (N=238). In contrast, the researchers in the study by MohammadniaMotlagh et al. (2022) focused on the effectiveness of a theory-based educational program for prediabetic women (n=80). Lastly, in the RCT by Shamizadeh et al. (2019), the researchers aimed to investigate the effectiveness of an

SCT-based intervention to promote physical activity in prediabetic individuals residing in a rural area (Shamizadeh et al., 2019). A commonality among these studies was that they all presented a statistically significant decrease in glucose levels. Hence, research supports the idea that programs that utilize SCT as a framework may yield significant findings.

Furthermore, three studies adapted their programs to be culturally sensitive (Datarian & Bowen, 2019; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022;). The researchers in the RCTs by O'Brien et al. (2017) and Peña et al. (2022) were culturally sensitive by adapting their programs to be delivered in Spanish. Similarly, Datarian and Bowen (2019) also culturally adapted their lifestyle program by targeting a Southern population and educating the participants on how to eat a healthy Southern diet, which focused on a diet culturally sensitive to the Southern population (n=24). Examining populations and adjusting education and interventions based on cultural needs is imperative to ensure understanding (Datarian & Bowen, 2019; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022;).

Additionally, the study by Datarian and Bowen (2019) had several drawbacks, including a limited participant pool, a single-group study without randomization, and a brief study period. However, the strengths of this study were a significant improvement in weight, dietary habits, and physical activity. The study by Datarian and Bowen (2019) had a high proportion of male participants. Similarly, the RCT by Das et al. (2021) had a high proportion of female participants, which reduced generalizability to other genders in both studies. Another weakness in the studies by Datarian and Bowen (2019) and Das et al. (2021) was the lack of a control group. Although a weakness in the study by Das et al. (2021) was that it lacked power, the study yielded statistically significant findings with a reduced glycemic index, as discussed above, and a higher fiber intake.

In contrast, two RCTs focused on Latino populations; in the study by O'Brien et al. (2017), the researchers focused on comparing intensive lifestyle intervention versus metformin use among Latinas (n=96), while Peña et al. (2022) focused on implementing a DPP among Latino pediatrics (n=117). Moreover, the researchers studied a metformin-taking group and a usual care group that received DPP-approved handouts to compare the effectiveness (O'Brien et al., 2017). In contrast, in the study by Peña et al. (2022), the researchers provided weekly educational classes that included portion control and recommended decreasing the consumption of sugary foods and drinks and saturated fats, managing portions, and increasing the consumption of fruit, vegetables, and fiber intake.

In addition, family members were included in the education, and physical activity was supervised twice a week, with the third day up to the participant. These studies focused on Latino populations, which lacks generalizability to other racial and ethnic groups. However, it is essential to note that Latinos are at high risk of developing T2DM; therefore, research in this area is a strength (O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022).

Additional strengths of these studies include a statistically significant decrease in weight, waist circumference, and BMI (O'Brien et al., 2017), while the RCT by Peña et al. (2022) presented statistically significant findings with a decrease in 2-hour blood glucose, body fat percentage, and quality of life.

In the RCT by Kramer et al. (2018), the researchers implemented the CDC-approved DPP-Group Lifestyle Balance (DPP-GLB) program among older adults (n=134). A strength of this study was utilizing a temporary control group, and a delayed start allowed for a realistic look at potentially real-life conditions. However, generalizability was limited due to a lack of racial and ethnic diversity. A strength of this study was examining the effectiveness of DPPs among

older adults, a vulnerable population that would benefit from this information (Kramer et al., 2018). Furthermore, the study presented statistically significant findings in a decrease in weight, HbA1c, waist circumference, increased physical activity, and BMI.

Moreover, two RCTs evaluated the benefits of digital DPPs and had larger sample sizes; in the study by Katula et al. (2022), they had a total of 599 participants, and in the study by Toro-Ramos et al. (2020), they had 200 participants. In addition, in the RCT by Katula et al. (2022), the researchers aimed to enroll 20% over 65 and utilized health coaches for education delivery. The educational sessions covered current exercise recommendations, nutritional education on portion control, a well-balanced diet, regular meals, and T2DM prevention planning (Katula et al., 2022). The researchers in the RCT by Toro-Ramos et al. (2020) sought to investigate the effectiveness of a fully digital DPP (n=202). However, generalizability was lacking because the participants were primarily White and socioeconomically advantaged. In Toro-Ramos et al., 2020), there was also limited generalizability due to the participants reporting mostly female gender. Nevertheless, these RCTs presented statistically significant findings with a decrease in weight and BMI (Katula et al., 2022; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). Additionally, in the RCT by Toro-Ramos et al. (2020), the study had significant reductions in HbA1c, cholesterol, HDL, and triglycerides. Thus, digital DPPs are not only more accessible but can also present significant findings.

In the two RCTs by Katula et al. (2022) and Staite et al. (2020), the researchers had the participants use a wearable device to track the participant's physical activity objectively. In the RCT by Staite et al. (2020), the researchers studied a fully mobile system relying on individual engagement among prediabetic patients (n=200). A limitation of this trial was that it was fully mobile and was prone to technological issues (Staite et al., 2020). In the study by Toro-Ramos et

al. (2020), coaches were easily accessible to participants for support, and they received messages from their coaches daily. In addition, participants were also expected to log their exercise and nutritional intake daily and were able to receive feedback from the coaches (Toro-Ramos et al., 2020).

A lifestyle intervention RCT by Fritsche et al. (2021) targeted prediabetic patients who were at a higher risk of developing T2DM and used intensive lifestyle interventions to prevent diabetes; the study's weakness was that while the sample size was large (1,149), the sample size was unequal between the intervention group (N= 896) and control groups (N= 253).

Additionally, because the education was completed at various health centers, there was heterogeneity in the education provided (Fritsche et al., 2021). In the intensified lifestyle intervention study by Fritsche et al. (2021), diet, exercise, and weight goals were assessed via a questionnaire during each meeting and reassessed after the program. In comparison, the control group only had eight sessions and was advised to exercise for 180 minutes of weekly activity (Fritsche et al., 2021). Additionally, the researchers utilized the DPP recommendations for lifestyle interventions in their control group. They adapted their intensive lifestyle interventions for high-risk individuals in the intervention group (Fritsche et al., 2021). A strength of this study is that it presented statistically significant findings with a decrease in BMI, live fat, and glucose levels.

To conclude, DPPs and lifestyle prevention programs have the potential to decrease blood glucose levels but also have various other health benefits (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Shamizadeh et al., 2019; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). To increase accessibility, any individual can

teach programs, and training is recommended. Lifestyle coaches constitute a significant component in the success of the program. While a wearable device is an objective way to collect data, it is essential to consider technological difficulties. A standard limitation of most studies was a lack of generalizability and an insufficient number of evenly proportioned racial and ethnic participants in intervention and control groups. A threat to internal validity in the studies was using self-reported questionnaires, which increased the possibility of recall and response bias (Bootland et al., 2017). A strength of this body of evidence was that most of the studies were RCTs, rated as level II on the level of evidence; in contrast, the one quasi-experimental study reviewed is rated level III (Grove & Gray, 2019). Another strength of these studies was their various statistically significant findings. Additionally, the reviewed studies focused on various high-risk individuals, such as Latino populations, geriatrics, and pediatrics.

Effectiveness of Interventions in DPPs and Lifestyle Programs

The DPPs and lifestyle intervention programs included an organized and instructional program to promote and educate individuals in adopting a better lifestyle through dietary changes and increased physical activity (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). In addition to preventing the progression of T2DM, it is important to assess other health benefits that occur through the completion of DPPs and lifestyle programs.

Weight, BMI, and waist circumference were among the many variables considered in the programs, and there were statistically significant decreases in weight, BMI, waist circumference, and weight loss among various studies (Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022; Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Keck et al., 2020; Kramer et al.,

2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Shamizadeh et al., 2019; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). Additionally, waist circumference significantly decreased in four reviewed studies (Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022; Dorans et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017). Therefore, research supports that DPPs and lifestyle programs can positively affect weight and BMI, thus decreasing other health risks associated with obesity.

Moreover, the diagnosis of T2DM is made using the following lab parameters: FBG, HgbA1c, and OGTT. Therefore, each study utilized one of these lab parameters in assessing the effectiveness of the DPP or lifestyle interventions in preventing the diagnosis of T2DM. Moreover, there was a statistically significant decrease in HgbA1c levels among participants across seven of the reviewed studies, thus preventing the progression of T2DM (Ben-Yacov et al., 2021; Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022; Das et al., 2022; Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018). However, it is essential to note that HgbA1c was not statistically decreased among all reviewed studies (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; O'Brien et al., 2017; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). OGTT and FBG were also statistically decreased among reviewed studies (Fritsche et al., 2021; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022; Peña et al., 2022; Shamizadeh et al., 2019). The first-line treatment for hypertension is lifestyle interventions, including diet and exercise. Although all available data does not support this conclusion, certain studies show that lifestyle changes can lower blood pressure (Dorans et al., 2022; Shamizadeh et al., 2019).

Cholesterol was another variable measured in the reviewed studies. Elevated cholesterol levels increase the risk of stroke and myocardial infarction and are frequently associated with T2DM or obesity (CDC, 2021; Tsao et al., 2022). Therefore, lifestyle

modifications are often the first line of defense for lowering cholesterol levels (CDC, 2021; Tsao et al., 2022). According to research, lifestyle changes positively affect lowering cholesterol levels and increasing HDL (Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022; Ben-Yacov et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Keck et al., 2020; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020). As a result, research supports that DPPs and lifestyle programs positively prevent T2DM and can also effectively lower cholesterol levels. Therefore, educating individuals on how lifestyle modifications might favor cholesterol levels is essential to motivate participants in lifestyle programs or DPPs. In addition, the researchers in the RCT by Peña et al. (2022) assessed participants' quality of life; the questionnaire revealed statistically significant improvements in quality of life among the intervention group.

In addition, research supports that DPPs and lifestyle programs can increase physical activity among individuals (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Kramer et al., 2018; Peña et al., 2022; Shamizadeh et al., 2019). It is important to note that various questionnaires assessed physical activity. A similarity between the RCTs by Kramer et al. (2018) and Katula et al. (2022) was the utilization of the Modifiable Activity Questionnaire [MAQ] to measure physical activity. In comparison, the researchers in the study by Daftarian and Bowen (2020) utilized the REAP-physical activity (REAP-PA). The International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) was utilized by Shamizadeh et al. (2019) and Staite et al. (2020). Lastly, the researchers in the RCT by Peña et al. (2022) used a three-day questionnaire. DPPs and lifestyle modification programs have been shown in studies to dramatically reduce weight, BMI, glucose levels, and cholesterol while increasing physical activity. As a result, an individual's overall health improves. It is

critical to understand the manner of delivery of the programs and which may be more successful.

Mode of Intervention Delivery

DPPs and lifestyle intervention programs can be delivered face-to-face (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022), entirely virtual (Katula et al., 2022; Toro-Ramos et al.), a mixture of virtual and face-to-face (Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Kramer et al., 2018), or fully web-based (Staite et al., 2020) that relies on individual engagement. Additionally, the researchers in the studies by Daftarian and Bowen (2020), Das et al. (2021), O'Brien et al. (2017), and Kramer et al. (2018) used a group-based approach for their mode of delivery. Research supports that group delivery can increase the engagement of participants, and all studies presented statistically significant findings (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2021; O'Brien et al., 2017; Kramer et al., 2018). In the study by Kramer et al. (2018), the researchers gave participants the option of completing the program face-to-face or virtually. Additionally, Das et al. (2021) used a combination of face-to-face and video conferencing for their educational delivery. Research supports that fully digital DPPs with a lifestyle coach resulted in statistically significant findings showing decreased weight and BMI (Katula et al., 2022; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020).

Due to the severe health risks associated with T2DM, it is imperative to offer a digital DPP for those who do not wish to participate in a face-to-face program (Katula et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). In the study by Staite et al. (2020), the researchers implemented a fully mobile approach and did not utilize a life coach. However, this was the only study that yielded no statistically significant findings. Additionally, digital DPPs can also be beneficial for decreasing HgbA1c (Katula et al., 2022). However, in reviewing the available

literature, not all digital DPPs presented a decrease in HgbA1c (Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). A benefit of face-to-face DPPs is offering in-person physical activity classes to keep track of attendance and motivate individuals in a group setting (Peña et al., 2022).

There are obvious benefits to both face-to-face and digital DPPs. However, giving the patient a choice between face-to-face and digital DPPs is beneficial. Research supports the idea that allowing patients to choose increases their autonomy and likelihood of participating in the program (Kramer et al., 2018). According to a review of the research, DPPs and lifestyle programs are complete initiatives that can improve overall health and prevent the development of T2DM. Additionally, programs that did not include a lifestyle coach were unsuccessful. Moreover, despite the mode of delivery, there were statistically significant findings in many of the programs, emphasizing that prevention programs can be effective whether they are offered virtually, in a group setting, or face-to-face.

Additional Evidence-Based Practice Recommendations

Nutrition

The ADA conducted a comprehensive five-year literature analysis for a consensus report on diets recommended for T2DM and prediabetic individuals; the researchers concluded that no single diet could be advised for everyone because each person responds differently (Evert et al., 2019). However, according to the researchers in the study by Evert et al. (2019), the Mediterranean and low-carb diets were the most studied. Furthermore, an RCT conducted by Dorans et al. (2022) examined the effects of a low-carb diet in individuals with HbA1c 6.0–6.9%; this study found statistically significant findings in a decrease in HbA1c, FBG, body weight, fasting insulin, diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and waist circumference. A few strengths

of this study were its high participation rate and the large proportion of black participants, who are often understudied.

In an RCT by Blancas-Sánchez et al. (2022), the researchers evaluated the Mediterranean diet in prediabetic individuals using the food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) to assess food intake and the KIDMED questionnaire for assessing adherence to the Mediterranean diet. The results of this study presented statistically significant findings with a decrease in HbA1c, insulin, waist circumference, hip circumference, and arm circumference. A weakness in the study by Blancas-Sánchez et al. (2022) was a small sample size and short study duration; however, the study yielded statistically significant findings. In contrast, Ben-Yacov et al. (2021) conducted an RCT in which they compared the effects of the Mediterranean diet to a personalized postprandial-targeting (PPT) diet in which an individual wears continuous glucose monitors and a customized diet plan is created. Moreover, participants self-reported their diet via a smartphone application. The researchers discovered that the PPT diet was statistically more effective than the Mediterranean diet in reducing HgbA1c, fructosamine, total cholesterol, triglycerides, and increasing HDL. One of the study's strengths was comparing one of the most researched diets to a new medically creative strategy that provided statistically significant results. However, further research in this area would add to the robustness of the literature.

Research shows that the Mediterranean, low-carbohydrate, and PPT diets all led to statistically significant changes in FBG, HgbA1c, body weight, insulin, waist circumference, arm circumference, hip circumference, fructosamine, total cholesterol, triglycerides, and HDL (Ben-Yacov et al., 2021; Blancas-Sánchez et al., 2022; Dorans et al., 2022; Evert et al., 2019). Therefore, research supports the current nutritional recommendations aligned with ADA (2019), which says that not one diet can be recommended for all. The diet should be personalized per

individual or cultural needs, food insecurities, responses, and personal preferences. In addition, they advise that all T2DM and prediabetic patients receive the necessary nutritional education and support that would be provided in a DPP or lifestyle change program (Evert et al., 2019).

Physical Activity

Exercise is a significant component of lifestyle intervention programs and DPPs; the current recommendation for physical activity is 150 minutes per week (Daftarian & Bowen 2020 et al., 2018; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Shamizadeh et al., 2019; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020; Velluzzi et al., 2022). Research supports that 150 minute of physical activity a week, along with a lifestyle coach or educational classes through DPPs or lifestyle programs, can yield a positive physical activity response, thus decreasing other anthropometric measurements (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Fritsche et al., 2021; Kramer et al., 2018; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022). Moreover, using a behavioral component such as SCT for physical activity change can increase physical activity among individuals (Ben-Yacov et al., 2021; MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022; Peña et al., 2022). Furthermore, research indicates that DPPs and lifestyle interventions that include a structured plan with assistance or a lifestyle coach have a higher degree of success than DPPs or lifestyle interventions that do not use this method (Staite et al., 2020; Velluzzi et al., 2022). Therefore, incorporating the changes in nutrition and physical activity can yield better outcomes for individuals, thus decreasing the progression of T2DM. According to research, lifestyle interventions can positively affect an individual's health; therefore, understanding why underutilization is critical to eliminating obstacles, improving referrals, and encouraging enrollment in DPPs.

Barriers to Diabetes Prevention Interventions

Although research supports the clear benefits of lifestyle changes and DPPs, they must be utilized more. Only 1% to 2.4% of the millions of eligible patients are expected to enroll in DPPs (Katula et al., 2022; Keck et al., 2020). Additionally, Medicare has added the Medicare Diabetes Prevention Program (MDPP), which is offered as a covered benefit but remains underutilized (Katula et al., 2022). According to the CDC (2021), a considerable proportion of people are unaware of their prediabetes diagnosis, a significant barrier that may be overcome by increased screening. Lack of education can be another barrier to preventing diabetes; therefore, the researchers in the study by MohammadniaMotlagh et al. (2022) sought to investigate the effectiveness of a theory-based educational program for prediabetic women. Additionally, the study presented statistically significant findings regarding the decrease in glucose and increased knowledge, attitude, diet, and perceptions of behavioral control about physical activity (MohammadniaMotlagh et al., 2022).

Another barrier is a lack of family involvement; increasing family engagement will increase the individual's success and potentially decrease the progression of T2DM (ADA, 2020; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020). In the RCT by Vargas-Ortiz et al. (2020), family involvement was incorporated into the intervention. Results included statistically improved glucose levels in prediabetic patients compared to the individual care group. Additional barriers include patient and provider barriers because patients might decline participation, and clinicians might not refer patients if they believe they will not participate (CDC, 2022d; Keck et al., 2020; Voelker, 2019). Other barriers include individual patient motivation, insurance coverage, and clinicians' referral preferences based on specific patient needs (CDC, 2021b; Keck et al., 2020; Voelker, 2019).

Furthermore, data shows that using a prediabetes care champion increases DPP referrals (CDC, 2022b; Keck et al., 2020; Voelker, 2019). As a result, more significant emphasis should be placed on enhancing the use of prediabetes and promoting awareness of prediabetes prevention. In reviewing barriers, research supports possible solutions that rely heavily on appropriate education or theory-based education, family involvement, and addressing possible patient and provider barriers via education.

Summary

In summary, the research evaluated included various demographics, from pediatrics to geriatrics, informing the benefits of diabetes prevention among multiple populations. Research suggests that lifestyle modifications and DPPs can help prevent the advancement of T2DM. Moreover, lifestyle adjustments may have various additional health effects on one's general health, such as lowering the risk of dysmetabolism and cardiovascular disease. Research supports lifestyle changes that have been demonstrated to be effective in decreasing weight, BMI, blood glucose, blood pressure, and cholesterol and increasing physical activity (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Staite et al., 2020; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020). Additionally, behavioral change-focused lifestyle treatments and DPPs using the SCT have had encouraging effects. Moreover, research supports that DPPs and lifestyle programs are effective in various delivery forms, and one was not superior to the others, increasing accessibility. Additionally, lifestyle coaches were a significant factor in the individual's success (Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Toro-Ramos et al., 2020)

Hyperglycemia, elevated cholesterol levels, and hypertension play essential roles in cardiovascular health; regulating these parameters reduces the chance of a cardiovascular event, stroke, and even death. As a result, DPPs help reduce the advancement of T2DM and can significantly reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease (ADA, 2020; CDC, 2021;). However, despite their numerous advantages, DPPs need to be utilized more in practice, and the emphasis should be on raising prediabetes awareness. Providers play a critical role in educating prediabetic patients and ensuring their success in the battle against T2DM, so referring prediabetic patients to DPPs and lifestyle programs is crucial. Therefore, this project aims to implement a pilot theory-based diabetes prevention program guided by current evidence-based recommendations in a primary care clinic in Los Angeles.

Methods

Objectives

The clinic offers a six-month program with monthly virtual educational classes and handouts. However, patients are referred to this program for elevated cholesterol, prediabetes, or obesity. Therefore, the classes are based on overall healthy interventions and touch on prediabetes. Furthermore, the program does not focus solely on diabetes prevention, and no data is collected following the program. Therefore, this Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) project aims to implement an evidence-based pilot prediabetes protocol targeting prediabetic patients in a Los Angeles, California, primary care clinic.

Setting

This DNP project occurred virtually, and participants were selected from a primary care clinic in Los Angeles. The team comprises three internal medicine physicians, one NP, two licensed vocational nurses (LVN), three receptionists, and eight medical assistants (MA). The clinic also provides care for adults 18 and over and focuses on preventive care, acute visits, and chronic disease management.

Sample

Purposive sampling was utilized in this project with a proposed sample size of 15 participants referred to and elected to attend the prediabetes DPP, which is appropriate for a pilot project. The final sample size ended up being five participants because two participants dropped out midway. The guiding body of evidence included prediabetic adults over 18. Thus, this project will focus on adult clinic patients. Exclusion criteria included patients diagnosed with T2DM, pregnant women, and children.

Design

Researchers frequently use pilot studies to propose a study to assess further and improve study components such as variable measurement, interventions, and sampling procedures (Daniel, 2019). This DNP project sought to test the effectiveness of a pilot diabetes prevention program based on the latest evidence, the CDC's DPP recommendations, and other lifestyle change program guidelines (CDC, 2021; CDC, 2021; Daftarian & Bowen, 2020; Das et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Katula et al., 2022; Kramer et al., 2018; O'Brien et al., 2017; Peña et al., 2022; Toro-Ramos et al., 2022). The NP led the project, teaching ten weeks of classes weekly virtually on Monday evenings. The educational material was site-approved and presented on a PowerPoint presentation; educational handouts from the CDC DPP were sent to the participants after each class. The educational material included information on T2DM, prediabetes, T2DM complications, and lifestyle changes, including diet and exercise.

Additionally, teaching on measuring physical activity, nutrition, potential hurdles, life pressures, and how individuals may overcome them was discussed. A lifestyle coach is a significant component of the DPP program (CDC, 2021). Therefore, the NP was always available to support the patients. The patients could contact the NP via portal message or request a call if needed. Additionally, only site-approved educational resources were used in this project.

Operational definitions

A study's framework should include operational definitions for carrying out a study and measuring its outcomes (Grove & Gray, 2019). Additionally, examining these studies' variables will allow for assessing outcomes. For example, in this DNP project, operational definitions include the independent variable as the pilot prediabetes protocol (the change). In contrast, the

dependent variables below will be assessed, including weight, blood pressure, HgbA1c, and nutrition and physical activity self-reported questionnaires (the outcomes as a result of the change) (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Ethical Considerations

Before the implementation of this project, an approval letter from the Chief Medical Officer (CMO) and supervisor was obtained. Identifiable patient information was not used in this project. Consent forms and educational materials were provided. Survey data was collected via telephone, and the NP recorded the participant's answers. Data was downloaded to Excel, stored on the project lead's locked computer with Apple FileVault, and kept in her locked office. The DNP student applied for approval from the California State University's Fullerton Institutional Review Board (IRB). Two CSUF faculty members, Dr. Hannah Fraley, Ph.D., and Dr. Kristina Fortes, DNP, guided this project.

Planning the Pilot Prediabetes Protocol

In preparation for this project, the DNP student consulted with the director of the current educational programs offered at the clinic. She agreed to provide the pilot DPP via their health prevention program via the DNP student leading the project virtually. The currently provided educational material and program information were reviewed. This project aims to evaluate the effectiveness of a pilot DPP instead of the current clinic program, a generalized lifestyle change program. Educational material and program components were reviewed with the director of educational classes, the site supervisor, and the CMO for approval.

The educational program was condensed; thus, planning what material to include in each educational class and PowerPoint presentation was created and tailored to the patient population. An email was sent, and approval was obtained from Dr. Gans at Brown University for permission to use the Rate Your Plate (RYP; Gans et al., 2006) questionnaire (Dr. Gans, 04/16/2023, personal communication).

Methods of Evaluation

Demographic information on race, age, and gender will be collected. The data will be charted on a table, and results will be reported as means, percentages, and raw counts.

Anthropometric measures, blood pressure, and HgbA1c

The data was collected and analyzed using pre-intervention and post-intervention data, and patients were followed prospectively throughout the project. The DNP Team Leader collected anthropometric measurements, including weight and height, from the electronic health record. The information was utilized to calculate BMI. Blood pressure was analyzed using the clinic's machines and abstracted from the EHR. Laboratory analysis of HgbA1c was sent to and processed through the laboratory LabCorp. Once results are available, the DNP Team Leader abstracted the levels from the EHR that are already part of standard care. According to current clinic protocol, pre-intervention data was the last lab, and vitals were collected as standard of care and reassessed 12 weeks later.

Questionnaires

Physical activity and nutrition were measured using self-reported questionnaires. Rate Your Plate (RYP) is a close-ended two-page questionnaire that assesses nutrition

and provides a score on ranking the individual's nutritional intake and is assessed numerically (Gans et al., 2006; Grove & Gray, 2019). Moreover, RYP breaks eating habits into three categories: 24-40 means the patient can make many changes towards a healthy diet, 41-57 means there are some ways to improve, and 58-72 concludes the individual is making very healthy eating habits. The participants were asked if they participated in at least 150 minutes of weekly physical activity. The questionnaire was distributed at the beginning and end of the program to see whether there had been any improvement in physical activity and nutritional intake after the program intervention.

Data Managed

Currently, at the primary care clinic, prediabetic data is not an analyzed measure; thus, no pre-data will be available. Prediabetic participants were identified via chart review and logged on an Excel sheet by number; no identifiable patient information was used. The following continuous variables were collected at the start of the project, including weight, blood pressure, and HgbA1c, and accumulated after the project. RYP was collected pre-intervention and then post-intervention and descriptively analyzed to investigate if there was an improvement in nutrition and physical activity after the completion of the project. The data was entered into an Excel spreadsheet and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Additionally, the data was entered in QI macros for further analysis to evaluate the program's effectiveness, which will be utilized to calculate means, ratios, and percentages. Data was analyzed in aggregate form and presented in various charts and graphs to allow for the elucidation of findings. The DNP student will present findings to the clinic CMO and staff at the CSUF Research Day and submit an abstract to regional and/or national conferences.

Evaluation

The projected outcome of this DNP project is a reduction in weight, BP, and HgbA1c. In the prospective project, data was collected and assessed pre-intervention and post-intervention. Participants will have increased knowledge about T2DM and prediabetes with the HBM as the project's framework. Understanding of nutrition and physical activity will be assessed at the beginning and after the program via self-reported questionnaires. Percentage changes in weight, BMI, Hgb A1C, and blood pressure (all these measures are standard of care) will be analyzed. Unfortunately, as the CDC recommends, this pilot DPP cannot be completed over a year. After the project, the data will be presented to the clinic to discuss if a prediabetes protocol would benefit the clinic and the patients.

Results

To begin the DNP project, a comprehensive chart review was conducted to select eligible participants. This process occurred over eight weeks. The project lead reviewed eligible participants and contacted them personally between patient care, inquiring if they would like to participate. Initially, 12 participants were selected to participate, but due to attrition, the total number of participants dropped to seven, and two participants dropped out midway, ending with five participants in the final sample for the DPP pilot intervention. The five participants attended ten classes virtually led by the project lead, each covering a different topic, including T2DM, prediabetes, diet in T2DM prevention, physical activity, the importance of sleep, a deep dive into carbohydrates, stress relief strategies, and the need for support. This was a quality improvement project, so the data collected before the project were the most recent labs and vitals already in the electronic health record (EHR) as part of the standard of care at the clinic. The data collected included height, weight in pounds, BMI, blood pressure, and HgbA1c. After completing the classes, the participants returned as standard of care for the post-intervention data. A questionnaire was also collected pre- and post-intervention. The questionnaire used was RYP, which is a two-page, close-ended questionnaire that breaks eating habits into three numerical categories. Overall, the project's results trended with positive outcomes. Three participants had a reduced HgbA1c, while two had an increase of .1% (Figure 3). All participants' mean decrease in HgbA1c was 1.3% (Table 3). An incidental finding was that the two participants with a slight increase in HgbA1c completely normalized their cholesterol levels.

In comparison, one participant who reversed her prediabetes had a rise in cholesterol. This could be due to dietary changes. Every participant had a reduction in blood pressure, weight, and BMI (Table 3). Moreover, there was a mean decrease in systolic blood pressure of

9.3% and a mean decrease in diastolic blood pressure of 6.5%. Additionally, the overall mean reduction of BMI among all participants was 4.6%, and a total mean of 43 pounds was lost. See Figure 3 and Table 3 for a summary of the results.

The RYP questionnaire evaluated participants' eating habits pre/post-DPP intervention. A higher score was associated with healthier eating habits. There was a mean 16% increase in self-reported more nutritious eating habits across participants (Table 3). In the pre-questionnaire, one participant was already in the highest category, with no changes needed, but the overall score improved (Table 3). All other participants trended their responses in the middle category, noting that they had some changes to make to live a healthier lifestyle. Two participants stayed in the middle category but improved their scores closer to the highest category.

Two participants improved their overall score, placing them out of the middle category and into the highest self-reported healthy eating habits category. These results highlight the importance of reviewing dietary intake with patients and offering evidence-based recommendations. Moreover, some notable trends in the questionnaire included a decrease in eating meats high in fat, an increase in the weekly intake of fish, an increase in the intake of whole grains, and the consideration of the amount of salt intake with each meal. Three out of the five participants reported not participating in 150 minutes of physical activity in the pre-questionnaire. After completing the project, all five participants reported participating in 150 minutes of physical activity weekly.

Demographic Characteristics

This small yet diverse group initially included Filipino, Black, White, Armenian, and Hispanic participants. After two participants dropped out, the final participants were Filipino, Black, Armenian, and Hispanic. The participants were primarily female, with four females and

one male. Three participants fell in the age category of 30-40, while the other two were between 50-60. All participants were English-speaking.

Discussion

In this quality improvement project, the project lead sought to improve the process for prediabetes patients. To begin this project, a comprehensive literature review was conducted. Research supports and recommends DPPs for diabetes prevention as they cannot only prevent the development of T2DM but also aid in improving an individual's health with a decrease in weight, BMI, blood pressure, and cholesterol levels. Despite the potential benefits, the program is underutilized. The primary clinic has a once-a-month virtual class held over six months that focuses on overall health, including prediabetes, but there are other focuses. In comparison, the DPP recommends weekly classes that focus on prediabetes and the prevention of T2DM, specifically. Therefore, the project lead conducted a pilot DPP over ten weeks to assess the effectiveness of weekly meetings incorporating these targeted evidence-based prevention topics.

Data was collected from the EHR pre-intervention and post-intervention, and questionnaires were collected via telephone pre-intervention and post-intervention. The data was collected, analyzed, aggregated, and presented in bar graphs and a table, noting the overall percentile changes. There was a decrease in overall HgbA1c, weight, BMI, and blood pressure across this sample of participants. Additionally, there was an increase in overall healthy eating habits. It is important to note that despite a decline in weight, blood pressure, and BMI, two participants had a .1% increase in HgbA1c. An interesting incidental finding was that the two participants with increased HgbA1c normalized their cholesterol. In comparison, one participant who decreased her HgbA1c had a slight increase in cholesterol.

The HBM was the framework utilized in this project. It was imperative in this pilot DPP because the theoretical foundation of the model includes shifting health beliefs and behaviors when given health education and guidance from providers (Mohammadi et al., 2018). The HBM also emphasizes that if someone believes the actual risks attached to a diagnosis, they will be more inclined to make a change (Champion & Skinner, 2008). Usually, DPP classes are taught by lifestyle coaches, dieticians, or nutritionists. The project lead is an NP who reviewed and discussed lab results at an advanced level and has a relationship with her clinic patients. Since the project lead is an NP who deals with managing T2DM and the chronic health conditions attached to diabetes complications, she included this information in the DPP sessions, alerting the participants of the real, potentially life-threatening health implications attached to T2DM.

Therefore, this project highlights the possible benefits of having an NP-led DPP program conducted virtually for clinic patients. Although research supports the effectiveness of DPPs (CDC, 2021; Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Kramer et al., 2018; O' Brien et al., 2017; Shamizedeh et al., 2019; Staite et al., 2020; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020; Velluzzi et al., 2022), it is essential to consider that meeting once a week is a time constraint that is only attainable for some people. The CDC DPP recommends weekly sessions for the first six months and biweekly thereafter (CDC, 2022). Furthermore, some participants decided to refrain from participating due to weekly meeting requirements. Additionally, DPPs can be offered virtually, hybrid, or in person. This project was taught entirely virtually, which was also an issue for some participants and was the cause for some choosing not to participate and ultimate attrition. Therefore, when a clinic implements a DPP, flexibility with class offerings, such as weekly, monthly, virtual, hybrid, or in-person classes, is essential due to individual circumstances (Kramer et al., 2018).

Offering flexibility may draw in more participants, which will hopefully, in turn, improve patient outcomes (Kramer et al., 2018).

Although this pilot DPP had a small sample size, the data in this project reflected the results in the literature reviewed, which showed that DPP programs are not only helpful in decreasing HgbA1c but also have other potential health benefits, including a decrease in weight, BMI, blood pressure, and cholesterol (Dorans et al., 2022; Fritsche et al., 2021; Kramer et al., 2018; O' Brien et al., 2017; Shamizedeh et al., 2019; Staite et al., 2020; Vargas-Ortiz et al., 2020; Velluzzi et al., 2022). Future studies should continue to review the effectiveness of DPPs to increase their utilization as they are underutilized (Katula et al., 2022). Future research should examine the efficacy of DPPs taught by clinicians such as NPs. The data identified in this pilot DPP highlighted the benefits, and the use of DPPs should continue to be encouraged to improve patient outcomes.

Future Implications, Recommendations, and Sustainability

Due to the increasing number of people diagnosed with diabetes and prediabetes, it is imperative to act now. Healthcare providers have a duty to promote health and encourage their patients to go on the right path to a healthy lifestyle (Hubert et al., 2021). Moreover, they must provide education on the dangers of a prediabetes diagnosis and what this means. They must diligently encourage DPPs and healthy lifestyle interventions to prevent T2DM and improve overall health, as research supports that DPPs can improve health outcomes (Hubert et al., 2021). Clinics should offer DPPs to all prediabetic patients, but it is up to the healthcare provider to refer and educate them on the importance of acting now.

Recommendations for future implementation of DPPs are to be mindful of possible time constraints and be flexible with class offerings (Katula et al., 2022). This includes the frequency

of offerings and the mode of delivery of the class offerings. Other recommendations are continued research in this area with larger sample sizes and the teaching of DPP classes by advanced practicing clinicians such as NPs. The effectiveness of DPPs taught by clinicians should be evaluated to address questions about the disease process, laboratory findings, and possible complications attached to T2DM.

Sustainability is essential in continuing the success of a DPP (Katula et al., 2022). To continue and adopt the CDC DPP, the clinic would have to change its current program from once monthly to weekly and follow the recommendations of the DPP. The clinic has the platform to do so and would need to explore how to change the current program to a DPP program with flexible meeting times, including a weekly option recommended by the CDC (CDC, 2021). As mentioned, healthcare providers play a significant role in making patients aware of and referring to the programs. So, for sustainability, healthcare providers must do their part in ensuring that patients are aware of their diagnosis and attached health risks, educating them on making healthy lifestyle changes and referring them to the available programs to prevent diabetes.

Limitations

While this pilot DPP had positive outcomes, some limitations were also encountered. First, the sample size was small, with only five participants. Due to the program only being offered virtually, there was attrition, and some participants opted not to participate. The pilot DPP included self-reported questionnaires, increasing the probability of response bias (Bootland et al., 2017). Additionally, participants who elected not to participate may have responded differently had they participated, indicating the possibility of non-response bias. Lastly, the selected participants were primarily female and only from one clinic, reducing generalizability. Despite the limitations, there were several strengths in this pilot DPP quality improvement

project, including a reduction in several physiologic measures and improvements in healthy eating choices among participants.

Conclusions

T2DM is a serious health condition attached to various comorbidities that affects millions of Americans nationwide (CDC, 2021). Prediabetes is a risk factor in the development of T2DM and is reversible (CDC, 2021). Therefore, it is imperative to examine and implement interventions to reduce the diagnosis of T2DM. The CDC developed DPPs to combat the increasing number of those diagnosed with T2DM. Despite research heavily supporting the effectiveness of DPPs in T2DM prevention and other additional health benefits, they remain underutilized (ADA, 2021; CDC, 2021a; O'Brien et al., 2017). The pilot DPP conducted in this DNP project highlighted the potential benefits of DPPs with an overall decrease in HgbA1c among the participants. Additionally, all participants had a reduction in weight, BMI, and blood pressure.

This pilot DPP highlighted the importance of DPPs in clinical practice due to their positive health benefits. DPPs should be encouraged for use in the clinical setting, and healthcare providers must do their part in educating and referring patients. The CDC recommends weekly meetings for the first six months and biweekly after (CDC, 2021). This allows patients to check in frequently and ask the necessary questions. DPPs align with the HBM foundation because the information in DPPs educates individuals on potential health risks associated with T2DM and the importance of making changes at the prediabetes diagnosis (ADA, 2021; CDC, 2021a; O'Brien et al., 2017). There was also a possible benefit of the classes taught by a clinician because clinicians can discuss disease, disease process and prevention, and laboratory findings at an advanced level (Davidson, 2021). Additionally, they can effectively answer questions about their

health. To conclude, T2DM is a severe health condition, and DPPs can aid in the fight against T2DM and should continue to be utilized in hopes of preventing TS2M and improving the overall health of individuals.

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Appendix A

Figure 1. Health Belief Model (Champion & Skinner, p. 49, 2008).

Appendix B

Figure 2: Theoretical Application of Theory of Planned Behavior

Appendix C

Table 1 Evidence for Literature Review

Database: Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Search

Terms	Limits	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Prediabetes	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2018-2023	4,716	4,716	20	0
DPP	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	1,021	1,020	50	1
Diabetes prevention	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	972	972	50	0
DPP and RCT	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	10	9	10	1
Diabetes prevention and RCT	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	22	22	22	0

Database: PubMed

Terms	Limits	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Prediabetes	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	543	542	10	1
DPP	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	755	752	33	3
Diabetes prevention	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	3	3	3	0
DPP and RCT	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	13	11	13	2
Diabetes prevention and RCT	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	123	119	20	4

Prediabetes and diet	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	8	7	8	1
Prediabetes and exercise	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	17	15	17	2

Database: OneSearch

Terms	Limits	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Prediabetes	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	13, 179	13,175	3	0
Prediabetes RCT	English language, peer reviewed, published date: 2017-2023	147	147	11	0

Appendix D**Table 2 Demographics***Demographics of Participants*

Demographics	Number
Ethnicity	
Filipino	1
Black	1
Armenian	1
Hispanic	2
Age	
30-40	3
50-60	2
Gender	
Female	4
Male	1

Appendix E

Figure 3 HgbA1c Results

Appendix F

Figure 4. Blood Pressure Results.

Appendix G

Figure 5 Body Mass Index Results

Appendix H

Figure 6 Weight Results

Appendix I

Figure 7 Questionnaire Results

Appendix J

Table 3 Anthropometric Data Before and After

	Hemoglobin A1C:	Blood pressure:	BMI and weight:	Questionnaire:
Participant One:	Before: 6.2% After: 6.1%	Systolic BP before: 134 Diastolic BP before: 83 Systolic BP after: 128 Diastolic BP after: 75	BMI: Before: 40.84 After: 39.87 Weight: Before: 253 lbs After: 247 lbs	Before: 43 After: 55
Participant Two:	Before: 6.0% After: 5.7%	Systolic BP before: 130 Diastolic BP before: 80 Systolic BP after: 118 Diastolic BP after: 72	BMI: Before: 29.94 After: 29.23 Weight: Before: 169 lbs After: 165 lbs	Before: 63 After: 67
Participant Three:	Before: 5.7% After: 5.8%	Systolic BP before: 134 Diastolic BP before: 95 Systolic BP after: 117 Diastolic BP after: 78	BMI: Before: 35.99 After: 32.12 Weight: Before: 190 lbs After: 170 lbs	Before: 52 After: 62
Participant Four:	Before: 5.8% After: 5.6%	Systolic BP before: 121 Diastolic BP before: 74	BMI: Before: 30.42 After: 29.1 Weight:	Before: 50 After: 60

		Systolic BP after: 108 Diastolic BP after: 58	Before: 161 lbs After: 154 lbs	
Participant Five:	Before: 6.0% After: 6.1%	Systolic BP before: 115 Diastolic BP before: 76 Systolic BP after: 104 Diastolic BP after: 71	BMI: Before: 28.7 After: 27.4 Weight: Before: 200 lbs After: 194 lbs	Before: 48 After: 53
Patient overall average:	Before: 5.94 After: 5.86	Systolic BP before: 126.8 Diastolic BP before: 81.6 Systolic BP after: 115 Diastolic BP after: 70.8	BMI: Before: 33.2 After: 31.5 Weight: Before: 194.6 lbs After: 186 lbs	Before: 51.2 After: 59.4

Appendix K

Table 4 Percentile Changes

	Hemoglobin A1C:	Blood pressure:	BMI:	Questionnaire:
Participant One:	1.6% decrease	Systolic BP: 4.4% decrease Diastolic BP: 9.6% decrease	2.3% decrease (6 pounds lost)	27.9% increase in healthy eating habits
Participant Two:	5% decrease	Systolic BP: 9.2% decrease Diastolic BP: 10% decrease	2.3% decrease (4 pounds lost)	6.3% increase in healthy eating habits
Participant Three:	1.7% increase Incidental finding was a decrease in cholesterol	Systolic BP: 12.6% decrease Diastolic BP: 17.8% decrease	10.7% decrease (20 pounds lost)	19.2% increase in healthy eating habits
Participant Four:	3.4% decrease Incidental finding was an increase in cholesterol	Systolic BP: 10.7% decrease Diastolic BP: 21.6% decrease	4.3% decrease (7 pounds lost)	20% increase in healthy eating habits
Participant Five:	1.6% increase Incidental finding was a decrease in LDL cholesterol	Systolic BP: 9.5% decrease Diastolic BP: 6.5% decrease	3% decrease (6 pounds lost)	10.4% increase in healthy eating habits
Patient overall total:	1.3% decrease	Systolic BP: 9.3% decrease Diastolic BP: 13.2% decrease	4.6% decrease A total of 43 pounds were lost	16% increase in healthy eating habits

Appendix L Approval letter

Date May 17, 2023
To Education Program Director
From Community Medical Director
Re: Project Prediabetes Protocol for Diabetes Prevention: Arianna Lanier-NP

This letter is to show that I, **removed for confidentiality**, as the Director CMD of **Removed for privacy**, give permission to Arianna Lanier and Dr. Hannah Fraley (project lead) to conduct the project titled Prediabetes Protocol for Diabetes Prevention at the **Removed for confidentiality**.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the CMO **Removed for confidentiality** and the site manager **Removed for confidentiality**, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- (1) collect data, which will include selecting prediabetic patients and collecting the following measurements: weight, blood pressure, BMI, and HGB A1C
- (2) Access necessary documents/data
- (3) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project
- (4) distribute the following survey using the staff email: International Physical Questionnaire (IPAQ), Rate Your Plate (RYP)
- (5) Provide weekly educational classes

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project comply with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at **Removed for confidentiality** and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature: **Removed for confidentiality**

Signature: **Removed for confidentiality**

Name: **Removed for confidentiality**

Name: **Removed for confidentiality**

Title: Community Medical Director

Title: Site Supervisor

Contact Information:

Contact Information:

Email: **Removed for confidentiality**

Appendix M

Questionnaire Approval

LA

Lanier, Arianna

To: Kim_Gans@Brown.edu <kim_gans@brown.edu>

Sun 4/16/2023 6:40 PM

Hello Dr. Gans,

My name is Arianna Lanier and I am a Doctorate of Nursing Practice student at Cal State University of Fullerton. I am conducting a project on diabetes prevention and wanted to ask your approval in using the rate your plate questionnaire for my project. This project will begin in September 2023 and conclude in December 2023. I appreciate you taking the time to read this email.

Thank you,

Arianna Lanier, MSN, FNP-BC

GK

Gans, Kim <kim_gans@brown.edu>

To: Lanier, Arianna

Sun 4/16/2023 7:36 PM

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

Hi Arianna. Yes, I approve. Good luck!

Regards,

Kim

Kim M. Gans, Ph.D., MPH, LDN

Adjunct Professor, Department of Behavioral and Social Health Sciences

Director of Community Engagement, 2020-2022

Director, Institute for Community Health Promotion (now the Center for Health Promotion and Health Equity) 2010-2014

Brown University School of Public Health

<http://www.brown.edu/academics/public-health/centers/community-health-promotion/>

Box G-S121-8

13. WHOLE GRAINS <i>1 serving = 1 oz slice bread; ½ English muffin; 1 c. cereal; ½ c. rice, pasta; 5 crackers; tortilla; mini bagel, 3 c. light popcorn</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 3 or more servings a day , 100% whole wheat bread & pasta, brown rice, whole grain cereals, i.e., oatmeal, raisin bran, Wheaties®	<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes eat: 1 or 2 servings a day	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: mostly refined grains, i.e., white bread, white rice, saltine crackers, corn flakes, Rice Krispies®, Special K®
14. FRUITS & VEGETABLES <i>includes legumes</i> <i>1 c. = medium whole fruit or potato, large tomato or ear corn, 2 c. raw leafy greens</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 4-5 cups a day	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 2-3 cups a day	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 0-1 cup a day
15. COOKING METHOD <i>for vegetables, pasta, rice</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually prepare: without fat & sauces OR use vegetable oil spray	<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes prepare: with sauce, butter, margarine, oil	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually prepare: with sauce, butter, margarine, oil
16. FAT TYPE IN COOKING <i>includes baking</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: olive or Canola oil Or, usually cook without added fat.	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: other oils, tub margarine	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: butter, bacon drippings, stick margarine, lard, shortening
17. SALT FROM PROCESSED FOODS	<input type="checkbox"/> Always/usually: <i>compare and choose lower-sodium options</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes: <i>consider sodium content</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Rarely/never: <i>consider sodium content</i>
18. SPREADS <i>added at the table on bread, potatoes, vegetables, pancakes, sandwiches, etc.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: spray or light tub margarine Or, seldom use.	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: regular tub margarine	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: butter or stick margarine
19. SALAD DRESSINGS, MAYONNAISE	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: fat-free or low-fat salad dressings & mayonnaise Or, seldom use.	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: light salad dressings & mayonnaise	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually use: regular salad dressings & mayonnaise
20. SNACK FOODS	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: plain pretzels, light popcorn, baked chips Or, seldom eat.	<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes eat: regular chips & popcorn, flavored pretzels	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually/often eat: regular chips & popcorn
21. NUTS, SEEDS <i>includes nut butters</i> <i>serving size = 1/4 c. nuts, 2 T. peanut butter</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 3 servings or more a week	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 1-2 servings a week	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 1 or less serving a week Or, seldom eat.
22. FROZEN DESSERTS	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: sherbet, sorbet, fruit juice bars, low-fat ice cream or frozen yogurt Or, seldom eat.	<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes eat: regular ice cream, ice cream bars/sandwiches	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: regular ice cream, ice cream bars/sandwiches
23. SWEETS, PASTRIES, CANDY	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: angel food cake, low-fat or fat-free products Or, seldom eat.	<input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes eat: donuts, cookies, cake, pie, pastry, or chocolate candy	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually/often eat: donuts, cookies, cake, pie, pastry or chocolate candy
24. EATING OUT <i>eat in or take out, any meal</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Seldom eat out Or, usually choose lower-fat menu items	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 1-2 times a week	<input type="checkbox"/> Usually eat: 3 times a week or more

Find your Rate Your Plate score:

Total checks in column A = _____ x 3 = _____

Total checks in column B = _____ x 2 = _____

Total checks in column C = _____ x 1 = _____

TOTAL _____

If your score is:

58 - 72: You are making many healthy choices.

41 - 57: There are some ways you can make your eating habits healthier.

24 - 40: There are many ways you can make your eating habits healthier.

Look at your Rate Your Plate responses.

Do you have any responses in Column A? If you do, great! You are already making some heart healthy choices. Look at your responses in Columns B and C. Where you checked Column C, can you start eating more like Column B? Over time, move toward Column A.

Think about changes. Write down eating changes you are **ready to consider**.

Change #1: _____

Change #2: _____

Change #3: _____

Begin today. Make changes a little at a time. Let your new way of eating become a healthy habit.

Set goals. After discussion with your doctor, write down eating changes you are **ready to work on**.

Goal 1: _____

Goal 2: _____

Goal 3: _____